

**EXPLORING THE CLINICAL AND BIOCHEMICAL LANDSCAPE OF TYPE 2
DIABETES MELLITUS IN MALE PATIENTS****ИЗУЧЕНИЕ КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ И БИОХИМИЧЕСКОЙ КАРТИНЫ САХАРНОГО
ДИАБЕТА 2 ТИПА У ПАЦИЕНТОВ МУЖСКОГО ПОЛА****ERKAK BEMORLARDA 2-TOIFA QANDLI DIABETNING KLINIK VA BIOKIMYOVIY
KECHISHINI O'RGANISH**

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Abstract. Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is a chronic metabolic disorder primarily characterized by insulin resistance and impaired glucose metabolism. The disease affects men and women differently, with male patients exhibiting distinct clinical presentations, risk factors, and biochemical profiles. This paper explores the clinical and biochemical aspects of T2DM in male patients, with a focus on the role of testosterone, fat distribution, and cardiovascular risks in disease manifestation. Understanding these gender-specific factors is crucial for developing targeted treatment approaches, improving disease outcomes, and reducing complications in male patients.

Keywords. Type 2 diabetes mellitus, insulin resistance, male patients, testosterone, cardiovascular risk, clinical presentation, biochemical alterations.

Аннотация. Сахарный диабет 2 типа (СД2) – хроническое метаболическое заболевание, характеризующееся преимущественно инсулинорезистентностью и нарушением метаболизма глюкозы. Заболевание поражает мужчин и женщин по-разному: у пациентов мужского пола наблюдаются различные клинические проявления, факторы риска и биохимические профили. В данной статье исследуются клинические и биохимические аспекты СД2 у пациентов мужского пола с акцентом на роль тестостерона, распределение жира и сердечно-сосудистые риски в манифестации заболевания. Понимание этих гендерно-специфичных факторов имеет решающее значение для разработки целенаправленных подходов к лечению, улучшения исходов заболевания и снижения осложнений у пациентов мужского пола.

Ключевые слова. Сахарный диабет 2 типа, инсулинорезистентность, пациенты мужского пола, тестостерон, сердечно-сосудистый риск, клинические проявления, биохимические изменения.

Annotatsiya. 2-toifa qandli diabet (QD2) surunkali metabolik kasallik bo'lib, asosan insulin qarshiligi va glyukoza almashinuvining buzilishi bilan tavsiflanadi. Kasallik erkaklar va ayollarga turlicha ta'sir qiladi, erkak bemorlarda turli xil klinik ko'rinishlar, xavf omillari va biokimyoviy profillar mavjud. Ushbu maqola testosteron, yog' tarqalishi va kasallikning namoyon bo'lishida yurak-qon tomir xavfining o'rniga urg'u berib, erkak bemorlarda QD2ning klinik va biokimyoviy jihatlarini o'rganadi. Erkak jinsga xos omillarni tushunish maqsadli davolash yondashuvlarini ishlab chiqish, natijalarni yaxshilash va ushbu bemorlarda asoratlarni kamaytirish uchun juda muhimdir.

Kalit so'zlar: 2-toifa qandli diabet, insulin qarshiligi, erkak bemorlar, testosteron, yurak-qon tomir xavfi, klinik ko'rinishlar, biokimyoviy o'zgarishlar

Introduction. Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is a global health challenge that affects millions, with approximately 422 million adults living with diabetes in 2021 (World Health Organization, 2021). Men, in particular, are more prone to developing T2DM earlier and with fewer symptoms than women, which results in delayed diagnoses and worse disease outcomes. This gender

disparity in T2DM incidence and progression is influenced by several factors, including differences in fat distribution, hormonal fluctuations, and lifestyle behaviors (Sharma & Prakash, 2020).

Men tend to accumulate visceral fat, which is associated with more severe insulin resistance and a higher risk of cardiovascular disease (CVD). Testosterone, the primary male sex hormone, also plays a critical role in glucose metabolism, with low levels contributing to insulin resistance and metabolic syndrome (Grossmann & Wittert, 2021). This paper aims to explore the clinical presentation, biochemical pathways, and risk factors unique to male T2DM patients, emphasizing how these factors contribute to disease progression and how gender-specific interventions can improve treatment outcomes.

Clinical Presentation of Type 2 Diabetes in Men

1. Symptoms and Diagnosis. T2DM presents similarly in men and women, with symptoms such as polyuria, polydipsia, and fatigue. However, men often experience a delayed onset of symptoms and are diagnosed at a later stage compared to women. Men are less likely to report early symptoms of hyperglycemia, leading to a more advanced state of the disease by the time of diagnosis (International Diabetes Federation, 2021).

In addition to delayed symptom recognition, men also face barriers in healthcare-seeking behavior. Men are less likely than women to undergo routine screening for diabetes, which contributes to late-stage diagnoses and poorer glycemic control. Men typically have higher fasting plasma glucose levels and more pronounced insulin resistance at the time of diagnosis compared to women (American Diabetes Association, 2023).

2. Obesity and Abdominal Fat Distribution. A major distinguishing factor in the progression of T2DM between genders is fat distribution. Men are more likely to store fat viscerally, rather than subcutaneously, which has significant implications for insulin resistance. Visceral fat is metabolically active and produces inflammatory cytokines, such as TNF- α and IL-6, which interfere with insulin signaling pathways (Ferrannini & DeFronzo, 2022).

Men with central obesity exhibit more severe insulin resistance and are more prone to cardiovascular complications compared to women of similar BMI but with different fat distribution patterns (Reaven, 2021). This visceral adiposity leads to an increased release of free fatty acids (FFAs), which are taken up by the liver, exacerbating hepatic insulin resistance and elevating blood glucose levels. Understanding the role of fat distribution in T2DM is crucial for developing gender-specific prevention and treatment strategies.

3. Cardiovascular Complications. Men with T2DM are at a significantly higher risk for cardiovascular diseases (CVD), including myocardial infarction, stroke, and peripheral artery disease. Cardiovascular complications are not only more prevalent but also more severe in male patients. Men with T2DM are twice as likely as women to experience major cardiovascular events, even after adjusting for other risk factors such as age and lifestyle (Circulation, 2022).

Dyslipidemia, characterized by elevated triglycerides and reduced HDL cholesterol, is more common in men with T2DM and plays a central role in the development of atherosclerosis. Additionally, endothelial dysfunction, often exacerbated by chronic hyperglycemia in men, accelerates the progression of cardiovascular disease. Aggressive management of cardiovascular risk factors in male T2DM patients is essential to prevent complications and improve long-term outcomes.

Biochemical Pathways and Mechanisms.

1. Insulin Resistance and Glucose Metabolism. Insulin resistance, the hallmark of T2DM, occurs when peripheral tissues, such as skeletal muscle and liver, become less responsive to insulin, leading to impaired glucose uptake and hyperglycemia. In men, insulin resistance is more closely associated with visceral fat accumulation, which releases pro-inflammatory cytokines that activate stress kinases like JNK and IKK- β , disrupting insulin signaling pathways (Ferrannini & DeFronzo, 2022).

Visceral adipose tissue also releases FFAs, which accumulate in the liver and skeletal muscle, leading to lipotoxicity and further impairing insulin sensitivity. This process is more pronounced in men due to the higher levels of visceral fat, which contributes to more severe insulin resistance and worsened metabolic outcomes.

2. Hormonal Influences: The Role of Testosterone. Testosterone, a key male sex hormone, plays a pivotal role in regulating glucose metabolism and insulin sensitivity. Low testosterone levels, commonly observed in men with T2DM, are associated with increased visceral fat, reduced muscle mass, and greater insulin resistance (Grossmann & Wittert, 2021).

Testosterone influences insulin sensitivity by promoting glucose uptake in skeletal muscle and regulating adipose tissue distribution. Testosterone replacement therapy (TRT) has been shown to improve insulin sensitivity in men with low testosterone levels, leading to better glycemic control and reductions in visceral fat (Sharma & Prakash, 2020). However, the long-term safety of TRT, particularly concerning cardiovascular risks, remains a subject of ongoing research.

3. Inflammatory Markers and Oxidative Stress. Chronic inflammation is a key contributor to the pathogenesis of T2DM, particularly in men with visceral obesity. Pro-inflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α , IL-6, and CRP are elevated in T2DM patients and lead to systemic insulin resistance by disrupting insulin signaling pathways. Male T2DM patients have higher levels of inflammatory markers compared to female patients, correlating with more severe insulin resistance and increased cardiovascular complications (Journal of Clinical Endocrinology & Metabolism, 2021).

Oxidative stress, characterized by the overproduction of reactive oxygen species (ROS), further exacerbates insulin resistance by impairing insulin receptor function and promoting beta-cell dysfunction. This is particularly relevant in male patients, who tend to experience greater oxidative stress due to higher visceral fat levels and reduced antioxidant defenses.

Risk Factors Unique to Male Patients

1. Lifestyle Factors. Men's lifestyle choices, such as diet, physical activity, and alcohol consumption, significantly contribute to the development and progression of T2DM. Men are more likely than women to consume diets high in processed foods, sugary drinks, and red meats, all of which increase insulin resistance and promote the accumulation of visceral fat (American Diabetes Association, 2023). Additionally, men often engage in less frequent exercise, further contributing to obesity and metabolic dysfunction.

Excessive alcohol consumption, more prevalent in men, exacerbates insulin resistance and liver dysfunction. Chronic alcohol intake is associated with an increased risk for fatty liver disease, a condition that worsens insulin resistance and complicates diabetes management. Moreover, smoking, which is also more common in men, further exacerbates T2DM by promoting oxidative stress and endothelial damage, increasing cardiovascular risk (Circulation, 2022).

2. Age and Genetic Predisposition. The risk of T2DM increases with age, particularly in men, due to age-related declines in insulin sensitivity and beta-cell function. Men also have a genetic predisposition to developing T2DM, particularly those with a family history of the disease. Several genetic variants linked to insulin resistance are more prevalent in men, underscoring the importance of genetic factors in the development of T2DM (Nature Genetics, 2022).

Management Strategies for Type 2 Diabetes in Men

1. Pharmacological Interventions. Pharmacological treatments for T2DM include oral hypoglycemic agents like metformin, sulfonylureas, and DPP-4 inhibitors. However, considering the unique biochemical and clinical features of T2DM in men, personalized treatment approaches are necessary. Testosterone replacement therapy (TRT) is increasingly being explored as an adjunctive therapy for men with T2DM and hypogonadism. Studies have shown that TRT can reduce visceral fat and improve insulin sensitivity, but long-term safety studies are still required (Grossmann & Wittert, 2021).

SGLT2 inhibitors and GLP-1 receptor agonists, which are effective in improving glycemic control and reducing cardiovascular risks, should be prioritized in men with T2DM and a high risk of cardiovascular complications. These drugs have shown cardioprotective effects in clinical trials, making them particularly suitable for male patients (American Diabetes Association, 2023).

2. Lifestyle Modifications. Lifestyle interventions remain essential for managing T2DM in men. Weight loss through a combination of aerobic and resistance exercise is particularly effective in improving insulin sensitivity and reducing visceral fat (Diabetes Care, 2023). Men who engaged in

regular physical activity experienced significant improvements in glycemic control and reductions in cardiovascular risk compared to sedentary men.

Dietary interventions, such as the Mediterranean diet, which is rich in whole grains, lean proteins, and healthy fats, have been shown to improve metabolic outcomes in men with T2DM. Reducing processed carbohydrates, sugary beverages, and saturated fats can lower blood glucose levels and reduce the risk of cardiovascular complications (Sharma & Prakash, 2020).

3. Monitoring and Prevention of Cardiovascular Complications. Given the increased cardiovascular risks in men with T2DM, regular monitoring of blood pressure, lipid profiles, and cardiovascular function is crucial. Aggressive management of dyslipidemia with statins, and blood pressure control with ACE inhibitors or ARBs, is recommended to mitigate cardiovascular complications. Cardioprotective agents like GLP-1 receptor agonists or SGLT2 inhibitors should be considered early in the treatment plan for male patients at high cardiovascular risk (Circulation, 2022).

Conclusion. The clinical and biochemical landscape of T2DM in male patients is distinct from that in females, driven by differences in fat distribution, testosterone levels, and cardiovascular risk factors. Tailored prevention and treatment strategies that account for these gender-specific differences are critical to improving health outcomes in men with T2DM. Ongoing research into testosterone replacement therapy and other gender-specific interventions holds promise for enhancing glycemic control and reducing complications in male patients.

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